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Study and Development of Manufacturing Technology for Polycrystalline Thermoelectric Materials of P-Branched Based on Bismuth and Antimony Telluride

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the development and manufacturing technology of p-type polycrystalline thermoelectric materials based on bismuth and antimony telluride. These materials are essential for thermoelectric generators operating within 300-500 K. Traditional methods utilize Bi_2Te_3 solid solutions with various dopants to optimize thermoelectric properties. This work focuses on synthesizing p-type materials using 74 mol.% Sb_2Te_3 and 26 mol.% Bi_2Te_3 . The effects of excess tellurium and selenium on thermoelectric properties were studied, revealing that tellurium enhances performance more effectively. Optimal doping concentration and annealing conditions were determined, achieving a significant figure of merit (ZT) in the desired temperature range. The results suggest that the developed p-type material can effectively pair with n-type elements for efficient thermoelectric converters.

Keywords: Bi_2Te_3 , thermoelectric

1. Introduction

It is known that thermoelectric generators made from semiconductor materials operate based on their p-type and n-type elements, which are manufactured in the form of briquettes. When these are connected in series and subsequently heated at one end in the temperature range of 300-500 K, various sources, including concentrated solar radiation, can serve as the heating source depending on the application. The main goal of the large-scale reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan is to ensure human rights and interests, and to create decent living conditions for our people. These reforms envisage the implementation of extensive measures aimed at raising the quality of education to a higher level. Currently, the method of growing single crystals is widely used in the cultivation of monocrystalline semiconductor layers and in the manufacture of various semiconductor devices: Seebeck or Peltier thermoelectric batteries, and in the production of thermoelectric materials. This method allows obtaining semiconductor thermoelectric materials and multilayer structures in a single process. Technological methods for growing and obtaining single crystals from semiconductor thermoelectric materials or substances, as well as for manufacturing structures, require innovative technologies

that are of great significance in science and technology.

2. Methods

Traditionally, solid solutions of bismuth and tellurium (Bi_2Te_3) with various dopants are used as the base material for thermoelectric generator elements, as these compounds have high thermoelectric characteristics [1]. In [2], the technological foundations for the synthesis of polycrystalline thermoelectric elements made from n-type Bi_2Te_3 solid solutions were described. It was shown that materials for the manufacture of thermoelectric generator elements (grown by the zone melting method or the Bridgman method) are crushed into small fractions and then briquetted by sequential cold and hot pressing and thermal annealing. The resulting material has an anisotropic polycrystalline structure, and due to deviations from structural stoichiometry and the introduction of dopants, the thermoelectric properties of the base material are optimized. In [3], the influence of excess Te atoms (up to 0.1 at.%) was studied, and thermal treatment of the samples was carried out in a spectrally pure argon environment at temperatures of 473 and 573 K for 120 hours. Measurement results show that small excesses of tellurium significantly affect the values of σ , α , and R at 77 K. Reliable measurements were conducted using the probe method along the length of the sample (ingot) in the temperature range of 77-300 K. Below, examples from foreign literature annotations are given: for instance, in the work of I. Saberi, S.A. Sajadi, H. Mansouri - The influence of the powder synthesis method on the thermoelectric properties of $\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_{2.7}\text{Se}_{0.3}$ thin films. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in...*, 2023 [13], it is stated that the purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of the $\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_{2.7}\text{Se}_{0.3}$ synthesis process on the thermoelectric properties of its thin films. Therefore, in this study, $\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_{2.7}\text{Se}_{0.3}$ powder was manufactured using two mechanical methods... [13].

In another work by the authors [14] B. Wang, H. Zhao, B. Zhang, D. Wang, A. Song, C. Chen, F. Yu, W. Hu, D. Yu, B. Xu - *Applied Materials and Interfaces ACS* 2023, the topic of "Enhanced Thermoelectric Properties of n-type PbTe by Optimizing Carrier Concentration over a Wide Temperature Range" is presented, where it is discussed that the optimal carrier concentration in thermoelectric materials increases with rising temperature.

However, conventional aliovalent doping typically provides an approximately constant carrier concentration over the entire temperature range, which can match the optimal carrier concentration only in a narrow temperature range. In this work, n-type PbTe doped with indium and aluminum was synthesized under high pressure followed by spark plasma sintering. While aluminum doping can provide an approximately constant carrier concentration at various temperatures, indium doping can capture electrons at low temperatures and release them at high temperatures, thereby optimizing the carrier concentration over a wide temperature range. As a result, both the electrical transport properties and thermal conductivity are optimized, achieving significantly enhanced thermoelectric properties in $\text{In}_x\text{Al}_{0.02}\text{Pb}_{0.98}\text{Te}$. The optimal $\text{In}_{0.008}\text{Al}_{0.02}\text{Pb}_{0.98}\text{Te}$ shows a peak ZT value of 1.3 and an average ZT value of 1, with a respectable conversion efficiency of 14%. The current work demonstrates that optimizing carrier concentration at different temperatures is effective for improving the thermoelectric properties of n-type PbTe [14].

The aim of this work is to develop a p-type material based on Bi_2Te_3 , obtained by melting components under an inert gas pressure for use in thermoelectric converters designed for temperatures of 300-500 K. Unlike Bi_2Te_3 n-type elements, producing the p-type counterpart encounters some difficulties. This is because when dopants that generate holes are introduced into the base, the thermoelectric parameters of the element deteriorate. For this reason, the production of effective p-type elements based on bismuth and tellurium solutions with practical parameters has long been a focus of specialists, and interest in this issue remains strong to this day [5].

Usually, for producing the base of p-type elements intended for the aforementioned temperature range, solutions with a composition close to $\text{Bi}_{2-x}\text{Sb}_x\text{Te}_3$ (where $x \approx 1.5$) are used. The batch is enriched with

an excess of tellurium (up to 4%) and various dopants creating acceptor levels (Se, Pb, Zn, Co) are introduced into the base. Generally, in thermoelectric materials, increasing the hole concentration leads to a decrease in the figure of merit of the thermoelement - ZT (where $Z = \alpha^2\sigma/\kappa$ - thermoelectric efficiency of the material, α - Seebeck coefficient, σ - electrical conductivity, κ - thermal conductivity). Recently, to optimize and improve the parameter values of semiconductor polycrystalline materials, the method of melting materials under inert gas pressure has been applied [3]. Depending on the pressure of the inert (argon) gas, the stoichiometry of the material, i.e., the structural periodicity of the atoms, acquires different values. This contributes to the alteration of the parameters of the resulting material.

3. Results

To produce the p-type element using the aforementioned technology, a solid solution composition of 74 mol.% Sb_2Te_3 + 26 mol.% Bi_2Te_3 was chosen as the raw material for melting the base. The thermoelectric properties of undoped alloys depend on the purity of the initial components. Therefore, in practice, it is not always possible to reproduce the necessary properties, as the properties of the resulting alloys change when switching from one batch of raw materials to another. Typically, the properties of alloys obtained under inert gas pressure correspond to the following parameter range: $\sigma = (800-1000) \Omega^{-1}\cdot cm^{-1}$, $\alpha = (210-200) \mu V/K$. In our case, the undoped base had $\sigma \approx 1000 \Omega^{-1}\cdot cm^{-1}$, $\alpha \approx 200 \mu V/K$. These values of σ and α served as the criteria for selecting the base material. The maximum ZT value occurred in the temperature range of $T \approx 320-340$ K.

Super-stoichiometric excesses of Te, Sb, and Bi lead to the following consequences: an excess of Te has a donor effect, increasing α and decreasing σ ; introducing excess bismuth and antimony into the batch, due to their acceptor action, increases electrical conductivity but decreases the Seebeck coefficient. The technology must allow for maintaining high Z values in the material during doping, which can be achieved by simultaneously deviating the composition from stoichiometry towards chalcogen enrichment and doping with lead.

Effective thermoelements from doped bismuth-antimony telluride can be produced only by appropriately enriching the base composition with tellurium. To optimize the material base parameters, the influence of tellurium additives in the initial alloy batch on its properties was studied. The results of the technological experiment are presented in Table 1. For comparison, the table also includes the results of studying the influence of excess selenium, as an analog to Te, on the thermoelectric properties of the base material.

Table 1a. This table summarizes the various properties and excess component weights for different compositions of the Bi-Sb-Te alloy system in 850 K.

Composition of Initial Components, wt. %	Excess Components, wt. %	$\sigma, \Omega^{-1}\cdot cm^{-1}$	$\alpha, \mu V/K$	$\alpha^2\sigma, \mu W/cm\cdot K^2$
Bi – 16,179	-	2590	104	28,0
Sb – 26,826	1,75 Te	1130	185	38,7
Te – 56,993	1,85 Te	1045	191	38,1
	2,0 Te	760	217	35,8
	0,75Se	1490	164	40,1
	0,85 Se	1235	169	35,3
	0,95 Se	950	206	40,3
	1,10 Se	807	216	37,3

Table 1b. This table summarizes the various properties and excess component weights for different compositions of the Bi-Sb-Te alloy system in 750 K.

Composition of Initial Components, wt. %	Excess Components, wt. %	σ , $\Omega^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$	α , $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$	$\alpha^2\sigma$, $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}\cdot\text{K}^2$
Bi – 16,179	0,25 Te	1200	185	41,0
Sb – 26,826	0,35 Te	1080	205	45,4
Te – 56,993	0,50 Te	667	220	32,3
	0,10 Se	1350	184	45,7
	0,20 Se	1030	196	39,6
	0,25 Se	770	210	34,0

As seen in Table 1, Te and Se have approximately the same effect on the thermoelectric properties. Although similar results can be achieved by introducing a smaller amount of selenium compared to tellurium, preference is given to the latter.

The analysis of technological experiment data showed that the p-Bi_{0.5}Sb_{1.5}Te₃ base for preparing half-elements should contain 0.25 to 1.0 wt.% excess tellurium, depending on the melting temperature and the diameter of the quartz crucible.

Figure 1 shows the temperature characteristics of the thermoelectric figure of merit for the p-Bi_{0.5}Sb_{1.5}Te₃ solid solution with different hole concentrations (curves 1-4). As can be seen from the figure, increasing the concentration of positive charge carriers by increasing the percentage of bismuth and tellurium in the base leads to a decrease in the amplitude of ZT. This is because increasing the concentration of holes (p) leads to an increase in σ , but at the same time, the value of α significantly decreases, and ultimately Z decreases. With increasing temperature, ZT sharply drops due to the influence of electron transport.

For comparison, Figure 1 also shows the dependence of the figure of merit on temperature in lead-doped samples (curves 5-6).

Doping the base with lead has the most satisfactory effect on the thermoelectric properties of the material in the range of $T > 300$ K.

This is because lead in the base, obtained with an excess of tellurium, forms lead telluride, which has a much lower vapor pressure than the vapor pressure of the Bi_xSb_{2-x}Te₃ compound. As a result, technological losses are reduced.

Lead was chosen as the doping additive for the following reason. Other impurities (Zn, Sb, Co), although they also act as acceptors in $A_2^V B_3^{VI}$ compounds and increase the concentration of charge carriers (holes), lead to a more significant decrease in their mobility compared to Pb additives [5]. The weak dependence of hole mobility on the amount of doping lead can be explained by the proximity of the atomic radii of Pb, Bi, and Te, as well as the main scattering mechanism being scattering by acoustic phonons [1]. Further adjustments to such materials concerning the dominant mechanisms are discussed in source [4].

To determine the optimal concentration of the doping additive, lead was introduced into the batch in amounts ranging from 0.05 to 0.25 wt.%. The effect of the amount of lead introduced into the batch on the thermoelectric properties of the Pb-doped ternary compound is shown in Fig. 2. From Fig. 2, it follows that with an increase in the amount of the doping additive, the electrical conductivity and Seebeck coefficient change almost linearly. The hole concentration also changes linearly.

The alloy with a Pb addition of 0.05 wt.% has the highest thermoelectric power. In this case, $\sigma \approx 1500 \Omega^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, $\alpha \approx 175 \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$, $p \approx 1.5 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The amount of loss decreases with increasing concentration of the doping additive, which is associated with the formation of a very thin layer of lead telluride on the surface of the melt, whose vapor pressure, as noted above, is lower than the vapor pressure of the synthesized compound.

To optimize the properties of the synthesized material, it is usually subjected to homogenizing annealing. The results of the changes in the base parameters before and after annealing at a temperature of 370°C for 17 hours are presented in Table 2. As seen from this table, after annealing, in samples doped with Pb in the range of 0.1-0.3 wt.%, there is an alignment of the $\alpha^2\sigma$ values. Although the $\alpha^2\sigma$ value slightly decreases during annealing, it is more important that annealing ensures the homogeneity of the polycrystalline material throughout the volume.

Table 2.

Doping Additive	Properties Before Annealing	Properties After Annealing
Pb, wt. %		

	Pb, wt.%	$\sigma, \Omega^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$	$\alpha, \mu\text{V/K}$	$p\cdot 10^{19}, \text{cm}^{-3}$	Pb, wt.%	$\sigma, \Omega^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$	$\alpha, \mu\text{V/K}$	$p\cdot 10^{19}, \text{cm}^{-3}$
0,10	1800	160	2,0	44	1100	190	1,2	40
0,20	2250	150	2,4	52	1250	185	1,3	43
0.25	2600	130	3,5	45	1600	160	2,0	41
0,30	2820	125	3,8	46	1700	155	2,2	41
0,40	3000	105	4,8	33	2000	135	3,6	36

One of the main criteria for selecting a base as half-elements in thermoelectric converters is the shift of the working temperatures of the substance towards higher temperatures. For this purpose, we investigated the temperature dependencies of the thermoelectric parameters of the base with different lead contents.

Figures 3 and 4 show these dependencies. Analyzing these dependencies, it can be concluded that the most optimal lead additions for producing the material are in the range of 0.25 to 0.4 wt.%.

From the data in Fig. 4, transitioning from the thermoelectric power coefficient $\alpha^2\sigma$ to the figure of merit Z, it can be observed that the latter parameter remains practically unchanged in the temperature range of 300-500 K. Considering this experimental fact, a base doped with 0.25 wt.% lead was selected for the synthesis of p-type half-elements.

4. Discussion

To obtain the working substance, the alloy produced using the technology described above was ground into fine fractions, as described in [2]. After mixing, the powder was sequentially subjected to cold and hot pressing and thermal annealing. The hot pressing temperature varied from 300 to 400°C. With a holding time of 5 minutes, thermal annealing was conducted for 17 hours. The measurement results (at T = 300 K) are presented in Table 3.

Technological Operation	$\sigma, \Omega^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$	$\alpha, \mu\text{V/K}$	$\alpha^2\sigma, \mu\text{W/cm}\cdot\text{K}^2$
Cold pressing	1300	120	19
Hot pressing at 300°C	2600	110	32
Annealing at 390°C, 17 hours	1450	160	37
Cold pressing	1300	120	19
Hot pressing at 360°C	2700	120	39
Annealing at 390°C, 17 hours	1550	160	40
Cold pressing	1300	120	19
Hot pressing at 400°C	2650	120	38
Annealing at 390°C, 17 hours	1550	160	40

5. Conclusion

The data in Table 3 indicate that the parameters of the samples are relatively insensitive to the temperature of hot pressing.

The developed p-type material [3-4], as well as the n-type half-elements, whose production technology is described in [1], can form an effective pair for creating thermoelectric converters for the operating temperature range of 300-500 K.

References

- [1]
- [2] B.M. Goltsman, V.A. Kudinov, I.A. Smirnov. Semiconductor thermoelectric materials based on Bi₂Te₃. Moscow: Nauka, 1972. 320 p. (In Russian)
- [3] E.T. Abdullaev, Sh.B. Atakulov, M.B. Nabiev et al., Geliotekhnika, 2008, No.1, 76-82. (In Russian)
- [4] G.Z. Bagieva, N.B. Mustafayev, G.Dj. Abinov, D.Sh. Abdinov, FTP, 2011, Vol.45, Issue 11, 1446-1449. (In Russian)

- [5] D.M. Zaichuk, On the dominant scattering mechanisms of charge carriers in lead telluride. FTP, 1997, Vol.31, No.2, 217-220. (In Russian)
- [6] M.B. Nabiev, Ya. Usmonov, T. Akhmedov, Sh. Yakubova, M. Sobirov, T. Azimov. Selected works of the International Symposium on Fundamental and Applied Problems of Science. Volume 3, (collective monograph). Moscow: RAN, 2013, Vol.5, 18-28. (In Russian)
- [7] M.B. Nabiev, M.A. Mamatova, Ya. Usmonov, G. Khusanova, A.A. Yuldashev. Fundamental and applied questions of physics. Materials of the international conference dedicated to the 70th anniversary of the Physical-Technical Institute of the "Physics-Sun" NPO, Tashkent 2013. 195-197. (In Russian)
- [8] M.B. Nabiyev, R.Y. Rasulov (1998), and others. IFJ, Vol.71, No.3, Belarus, pp. 542-543.
- [9] M.B. Nabiyev (2017), et al. Study of extreme operating modes in semiconductor thermoelements using the rectangular pulse mode in non-stationary thermoelectric cooling. International conference. Actual problems of physics and chemistry of polymer composites, as well as the technology of structural materials. 12-13 July. Namangan, Uzbekistan. pp. 126-130.
- [10] M.B. Nabiyev (2020) Monograph: Extreme operating modes of semiconductor thermoelements and devices based on them. Published by Classic. Tashkent-Fergana. Print run 100, p. 114.
- [11] M.B. Nabiyev (2022) Solution to the problem of the possibilities of non-stationary thermoelectric cooling using rectangular current pulses. SAMMITI-2022. Tashkent.
- [12] M.B. Nabiyev. Increasing the efficiency of thermoelectric materials. Education Scientific Journal, Vol.2, No.8, 2023, Uzbekistan.
- [13] M.B. Nabiev, T.K. Zhabbirov, I.I. Yuldoshova. (2022) Technology for manufacturing solders based on bismuth and lead for thermoelements. Research and Education. (In Russian)
- [14] I. Saberi, S.A. Sajjadi, Kh. Mansuri - Influence of the powder synthesis method on the thermoelectric properties of Bi₂Te_{2.7}Se_{0.3} thin films. Journal of Materials Science: Materials in..., 2023.
- [15] B. Wang, H. Zhao, B. Zhang, D. Wang, A. Song, Ch. Chen, F. Yu, V. Hu, D. Yu, B. Xu - Applied Materials and Interfaces ACS, 2023.